

carbon capture and storage

GUNDIH

MODELLING OF TIME-LAPSE SEISMIC AND GEOMECHANICAL ANALYSIS FOR CO₂ SEQUESTRATION MONITORING IN GUNDIH GAS FIELD

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OUTLINE

- Introduction
- Literature study
- Rock physics modelling
- Seismic modelling
- Seismic inversion
- Geomechanical modelling
- Conclusion

INTRODUCTION

Gundih Field

- Located in Blora District, Central Java, Indonesia
- Cepu Block
- Is a gas producing field
- + 21% CO₂ of total gas
- Emission 800 tons/day
- CCS started since 2012
- Pilot Project Plan: Injection into carbonate rock of Kujung Formation

3

Capacity Containment Injectivity

+

2

Safe Sustainable

Needs monitoring

OBJECTIVES

- Study how CO₂ changes the acoustic properties of carbonate reservoir rock.
- Identify CO₂ in a very deep carbonate reservoir using 2D land time-lapse seismic method.
- Study the applicability of 2D seismic survey for monitoring of CO₂ injection.
- Study how CO₂ changes the geomechanical behavior of the carbonate reservoir rock.

“Being an engineer always asks and solves.”

WORKFLOW

LITERATURE STUDY

CARBONATE BUILD-UP RESERVOIR

Purwaningsih (2002)

Yohanes Nuwara (12315059)

BASEMAP

DYNAMIC MODELS

Rate 150 ton per day
After 2 years (M1)

Rate 150 ton per day
After 10 years (M2)

Rate 800 ton per day
After 2 years (M1)

Rate 800 ton per day
After 10 years (M2)

ROCK PHYSICS MODELLING

CARBONATE ROCK PHYSICS

Factors Influencing on Seismic Velocities

04/05/2015

36

NORSAR
Seismic Modelling

NORSAR, 2014

Li et al, 2013

WELL DATA

MODELLING WORKFLOW

- **Step 1.** Calculate matrix density : 2.73 g/cc
- **Step 2.** Determine mineral composition : 40% calcite, 25% clay, 2% quartz, 34% dolomite
- **Step 3.** Calculate matrix bulk modulus : 58.38 Gpa → Voigt-Reuss-Hill
- **Step 4.** Calculate saturated bulk modulus : 37.51 Gpa → RHOB, Vp log
- **Step 5.** Calculate dry bulk modulus : 35.15 Gpa → Biot-Gassmann method
- **Step 6.** Calculate pore bulk modulus : 12.36 GPa

7. FLUID PROPERTIES

- Calculation method : FLAG / Fluid Application of Geophysics (developed by Colorado School of Mines)
- Fluid mixing type : Medium patchy (Brie exponent)
- Baseline P,T : 34 MPa, 159°C
- After injection P,T : 35.2 MPa, 159°C
- CO2 saturation is 50%, irreducible brine saturation 50%
- Fluid property calculation:

$$P = 35.2 \text{ MPa}, T = 159 \text{ C}$$

$$\rho_{fl,M2} = 0.4692 \text{ g/cc}$$

$$K_{fl,M2} = 0.5684 \text{ GPa}$$

8. KUSTER-TOKSOZ MODELLING

- Kuster-Toksoz to calculate saturated bulk and shear modulus, then saturated V_p, V_s , & density
- Reason why use KT : Difference between K_{sat} & K_{dry} is small, only 2 GPa

9. SEISMIC PROPERTY CHANGE

- V_p decreases by 80 m/s (1.8%)
- V_s increases by 23 m/s (0.87%)
- Density decreases by 2.42%

SEISMIC MODELLING

BASELINE MODEL

Lithology	P-velocity (m/s)	S-velocity (m/s)	Density (g/cc)
Kawengan Group	Increasing linearly	Increasing linearly	Increasing linearly
Ngrayong	2820	1239	2.20
Tuban	2400	921	2.15
Near MFS Tuban	2865	1273	2.25
Platform Interior	3820	1995	2.55
Ngimbang	3320	1617	2.15

Vp model

Density model

800 TON/DAY (AFTER 2 YEARS)

Vp model

Density model

800 TON/DAY (AFTER 10 YEARS)

Vp model

Density model

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ACQUISITION PARAMETER & PROCESSING

Length $\sim 1.2 * \text{target depth}$
(Vermeer, 2001)

Length = 5 km

Parameter	Value
Position	Crossline 6535 from previous acquisition
Seismic line length	5 km
Number of shots	251
Shot spacing	20 m
Number of receivers	501
Receiver spacing	10 m
Source frequency	50 Hz

SYNTHETIC RESULT (MO)

Last shot
(251)

SYNTHETIC RESULT (M2)

Last shot
(251)

DIFFERENCE (M2-M0)

Last shot
(126)

COMPARISON OF RESULT (1ST SHOT)

Frequency 50 Hz
Receiver spacing 40 m

Frequency 50 Hz
Receiver spacing 10 m

Frequency 10 Hz
Receiver spacing 10 m

ZERO-OFFSET UNMIGRATED SECTION

ZERO-OFFSET MIGRATED SECTION

POST-STACK TIME MIGRATED SECTION (BASELINE)

POST-STACK (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 150 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

DIFFERENCED SECTION

Injection Rate: 150 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

POST-STACK (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 800 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

DIFFERENCED SECTION

Injection Rate: 800 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

SEISMIC INVERSION

INJ-2 SYNTHETIC LOG AS WELL CONSTRAINT

INITIAL MODEL FOR INVERSION

Vp model

Density model

AI model

PRE-INVERSION ANALYSIS

Inversion method : Model-based
 Type : Constrained (hard constraint)
 Parameter : Max impedance change 25%,
 prewhitening 1%, block size 1 ms, iteration 100x

Result:
 Correlation : 0.973 (M0), 0.975 (M2)
 RMS error : 398.7 (M0), 392.9 (M2)
 Synthetic error : 0.25 (M0), 0.25 (M2)

Baseline

After 10 years (M2)

POST-STACK AI SECTION (BASELINE)

POST-STACK AI SECTION (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 150 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

DIFFERENCED AI (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 150 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

POST-STACK AI SECTION (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 800 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

DIFFERENCED AI (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 800 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

GEOMECHANICAL MODELLING

RESERVOIR GEOMECHANICS

(Verdon, 2012)

- Critical Pp: $P_{cr} = \sigma_{cr} + \frac{(C_0 - \tau_{cr})}{\tan \phi}$
- Critical angle: $\theta_{cr} = \frac{90 - \phi}{2}$

MODELLING WORKFLOW

INPUTS

- **Injection depth = 3400 m**
- **Period = 10 years (1 January 2019 – 1 January 2029)**
- In-situ values at injection depth (calculated from gradient data)
 1. σ_v = 70.71 MPa
 2. σ_H = 116.82 MPa
 3. σ_h = 57.64 MPa
 4. P_p = 29.05 MPa
- Parameters for Mohr-Coulomb envelope
 1. C_0 = 5.5 MPa
 2. ϕ = 28°

PORE PRESSURE CALCULATION

Pressure calculator:

$$dP = \frac{1}{V_p} \cdot \frac{dV}{\beta_f}$$

- In-situ pore pressure in 2019 = After production is 29.05 MPa
- dV = cumulative volume of injected CO₂ from 2019 to 2021, and 2029
- V_p = pore volume (porosity * bulk volume); bulk volume = $4.8 \times 10^{11} \text{ m}^3$
- β_f = pore compressibility (inverse of pore incompressibility) = 12.36 Gpa
- Maximum pore pressure increase (dP) after 10 years
 - Rate 150 ton per day = 0.6 MPa
 - Rate 800 ton per day = 1.2 MPa

MOHR-COULOMB RESULT

Increases only 0.6 MPa
Injection is safe

Rate 150 ton per day

Baseline

At 1 January 2029

MOHR-COULOMB RESULT

Increases 1.2 MPa
Injection is safe

Rate 800 ton per day

Baseline

At 1 January 2029

CONCLUSION

CONCLUSIONS

- V_p decreases by 1.8%, V_s increases by 0.87%, and density decreases by 2.42% due to 50% CO₂ saturation and increase of pore pressure in the carbonate reservoir.
- The use of receiver spacing of 10 m and source frequency 50 Hz in the acquisition improves the quality and resolution of CO₂ plume in the seismic data.
- Geometry of CO₂ plume is visible in the post-stack migrated time seismic data after processing and differencing.
- Post-stack inversion improves the imaging of CO₂ by showing the CO₂ plume as low impedance, with the use of 3 synthetic wells as constraint.
- From geomechanical perspective, the CO₂ injection with rate of 800 ton per day is safe for 10 years because the pore pressure increase (1.2 MPa) is still below the critical pore pressure. (5.5 MPa). It is safe for 40 years ahead.

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THANKYOU

BACKUP SLIDE ROCK PHYSICS MODELLING

KUSTER-TOKSOZ METHOD

- KT method is more valid in carbonate than Biot-Gassmann replacement method (BG)
- Carbonate rocks have variety of porosity & isolated pores
- BG does not include pore shapes, pores are connected
- KT includes pore shapes

$$\frac{K^* - K_m}{3K^* + 4G_m} = c \frac{K' - K_m}{3K' + 4G_m}$$

$$\frac{G^* - G_m}{6G^*(K_m + 2G_m) + G_m(9K_m + 8G_m)} = c \frac{G' - G_m}{6G'(K_m + 2G_m) + G_m(9K_m + 8G_m)}$$

$$\rho^* - \rho_m = c(\rho' - \rho_m)$$

Applicability	Biot-Gassmann	Kuster-Toksöz
Pore shapes	Not suitable for fractures	Any shape
Connected porosity	Yes	No
Pore interactions	No	No
Pore fluid flow	No	No
First order scattering	No	Yes

K^* : effective bulk modulus

K_m : matrix bulk modulus

K' : inclusion bulk modulus

G_m : matrix shear modulus

G^* : effective shear modulus

G' : inclusion shear modulus

ρ^* : effective density

ρ_m : matrix density

ρ' : inclusion density

c : inclusion volume concentration (or porosity)

1. MATRIX DENSITY

Process:

$$\rho_b = (1 - \phi)\rho_m + \phi\rho_{fl}$$

???

This interval (injection target) is 100% brine saturated
 ρ_{fl} calculated using FLAG 2014 method

100% Brine
 $P = 34 \text{ MPa}, T = 157.975 \text{ C}$
 $\rho_{fl} = 0.9365 \text{ g/cc}$
 $K_{fl} = 2.24 \text{ GPa}$

Result: transformed log

Average matrix density 2.73 g/cc

ESTIMATE MINERAL COMPOSITION

- Forward calculation : Search for any combination of calcite, dolomite, clay, and quartz fraction to approximate the matrix density for the most fit possible

$$\rho_m = \sum_{i=1}^N f_i \rho_i$$

Result:

Mineral	Density (g/cc)	Bulk modulus (GPa)	Shear modulus (GPa)
Calcite	2.71	76.8	32
Clay	2.58	20.9	6.9
Quartz	2.65	36.6	45
Dolomite	2.87	94.9	45

Mineral fraction (%)	Stratum 1 (include gas cap; 2777-2955 m)	Stratum 3 (reservoir; 3065-3500 m)
Calcite	80%	40%
Clay	5%	24%
Quartz	5%	2%
Dolomite	10%	34%
Calculated ρ_m (g/cc)	2.7165	2.732
Original ρ_m (g/cc)	2.71	2.73
Misfit (g/cc)	0.0065	0.002

3. DRY BULK MODULUS

Vp from log = 4800 m/s
 Vs from log = 2436.80 m/s
 RHOB = 2.48 g/cc

$$G_{sat} = \rho V_s^2$$

$$K_{sat} = \rho \left(V_s^2 - \frac{4}{3} V_p^2 \right)$$

$K_{sat} = 37.51 \text{ GPa}$
 $G_{sat} = 14.73 \text{ GPa}$

Result:

$K_d = 35.15 \text{ GPa}$

Gassmann's Fluid Replacement:

$$K_d = \frac{K_{sat} \left(\frac{\phi K_s}{K_{fl}} + 1 - \phi \right) - K_s}{\frac{\phi K_s}{K_{fl}} + \frac{K_{sat}}{K_s} - 1 - \phi}$$

Average $\phi = 0.14$

VRH method:
 $K_s = 58.38 \text{ GPa}$

100% Brine
 $P = 34 \text{ MPa}, T = 157.975 \text{ C}$
 $\rho_{fl} = 0.9365 \text{ g/cc}$
 $K_{fl} = 2.24 \text{ GPa}$

FLUID TABLE (FLAG CALCULATION)

Pore fluid	Pore pressure (MPa)	Density (g/cc)	Bulk modulus (GPa)
100% Brine	34	0.9361	2.24
50% CO ₂ + 50% Brine	35.4	0.4692	0.57
70% Gas + 30% Brine	28.7	0.150	0.70

FLUID PROPERTIES

Patch type: intermediate patchy

BACKUP SLIDE SEISMIC MODELLING

NORSAR-3D SEISMIC MODELLING

The image shows three overlapping software windows from a seismic modeling application. The 'Set Wave Front Plot Options' window on the left has several sections: 'Wave Front Plot Parameters' with checkboxes for 'Include Plot Of Wave Front', 'Include Fill', 'Include Triangle Lines', and 'Include Edges'; 'Include Contours' with options for XY, YZ, and XZ; and 'Remove Previous Wavefront' with clip low and high values for X, Y, and Z. The 'Trace Wavefront' window in the center features a 'Trace' button, a 'Write Messages During Tracing' checkbox, and a 'Set Technical Parameters...' button. It contains a table for 'Shot Selection' with columns for Xlines, Inlines, and Depth, and a 'Shot Type' section with 'Spherical' and 'Disc' options. The 'Set Technical Parameters' window on the right is divided into 'Wavefront Density Parameters', 'Removal Parameters', 'WF-Discontinuity Treatment', and 'Ray Tracing Algorithm'. A red box highlights the 'Maximum Distance Between Rays (km)' field, which is set to 0.10. A yellow callout bubble points to this field with the text 'Less than plume height = 121 m, 100 m is enough'. The 'Wavefront Density Parameters' section also includes 'Maximum Angle Between Rays (deg)' and 'Time Step Length (sec)'. The 'Removal Parameters' section includes 'Max Inc. Angle at EVERY Interface (deg)' and 'Max Dep. Angle at EVERY Interface (deg)'. The 'WF-Discontinuity Treatment' section includes 'Refinement Level' and a checkbox for 'Do not handle working box as a discontinuity'. The 'Ray Tracing Algorithm' section includes 'ODE Solver' and 'Accuracy' options.

Less than plume height = 121 m, 100 m is enough

8 KB	7/3/2019 11:20:30 ...	rw-rw-r--	nors
1 KB	7/3/2019 11:20:30 ...	rw-rw-r--	nors
8 KB	7/3/2019 11:19:50 ...	rw-rw-r--	nors
1 KB	7/3/2019 11:19:50 ...	rw-rw-r--	nors

SYNTHETIC RESULT

Shot 1, 2, 3, 4 (Baseline)

SYNTHETIC RESULT

Shot 1, 2, 3, 4 (After 10 years, M2)

DIFFERENCED SYNTHETIC RESULT

Shot 1, 2, 3, 4 (M2-M0)

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FREQUENCY 10 HZ VS. 50 HZ

Velocity 4800 m/s
Frequency 10 Hz
Resolution = $0.25 \lambda = 120$ m

Velocity 4800 m/s
Frequency 50 Hz
Resolution = $0.25 \lambda = 24$ m

Height of plume
121.6 m

10 Hz

50 Hz

RECEIVER SPACING 40 M VS. 10 M

Very much spatially aliased
(quality not good)

Group interval

$$GI = 0.5 \times \left(\frac{V_{min}}{F_{max}} \right) \times \sin(\theta)$$

$$\theta = 30^\circ$$

$$GI = 24 \text{ m}$$

Not spatially aliased
(quality good)

40 m

10 m

SEISMIC MODELLING METHODS

Quality is much better.

Plume is barely visible.

Wavefront construction method
(NORSAR-3D)

Ray shooting method
(NORSAR-2D)

View 1

Color Data: ZO_N2D_800tpd_M0
Inserted Data: Well Path

Seismic

View 1

Color Data: ZO_N2D_150tpd_M1_10Hz

Inserted Curve Data: P-wave

View 1

Color Data: ZO_N2D_150tpd_M2_10Hz

Inserted Curve Data: P-wave

View 1

Color Data: ZO_N2D_800tpd_M1_10Hz

Inserted Curve Data: P-wave

View 1

Color Data: ZO_N2D_800tpd_M2_10Hz

Inserted Curve Data: P-wave

BACKUP SLIDE SEISMIC INVERSION

SYNTHETIC ERROR

Baseline

800 ton per day, M2

INVERSION WITH REAL SEISMIC DATA

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View 2

Color Data: Z0_N2D_800tpd_M1_Inverted_Zp
Inserted Data: Computed Impedance P

- ▼ Favorites
 - Pre-stack
 - Post-stack
- ▼ Seismic
 - Pre-stack
 - CommonShot_SP1-51_case1_h
 - CommonShot_SP1-51_case1_h
 - CommonShot_SP1-51_case2_h
 - difference_cdp_25
 - normalized1
 - output_CommonShot_case2_2
 - trace_maths
 - Post-stack
 - Difference
 - Difference2
 - Image_SP1-101_case1_halfrece
 - Image_SP1-101_case1_halfrece
 - Image_SP1-101_case2_halfrece
 - Image_SP1-101_case2_halfrece
 - Linprog_inverted_Nuvara (Syn
 - Linprog_inverted_Nuvara_base
 - Modelbased_inverted_Nuvara
 - Modelbased_inverted_Nuvara
 - Seismic_Line_1_newnew
 - Z0_N2D_800tpd_M0_Inverted
 - Z0_N2D_800tpd_M1_Inverted
 - Z0_N2D_800tpd_M2_Inverted
 - ZO_N2D_150tpd_M1
 - ZO_N2D_150tpd_M2
 - ZO_N2D_800tpd_M0
 - ZO_N2D_800tpd_M1
 - ZO_N2D_800tpd_M2
 - Zp_inverted_difference
 - cdp_stack

INVERSION WITH ONLY ONE WELL CONSTRAINT

POST-STACK AI SECTION (BASELINE)

POST-STACK AI SECTION (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 150 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

POST-STACK AI SECTION (AFTER INJECTION)

Injection Rate: 800 ton per day

After 2 years (2021)

After 10 years (2029)

View 2

Color Data: Final_ZO_N2D_150tpd_M1_Inverted_Zp
Inserted Data: Computed Impedance P

